

Tool 14

The data collection protocol

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 2 – develop), which helps you in making design choices for the data collection protocol of your citizen science project.

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer. If you have any further questions about this template, please contact citizenscience@vub.be.

1. Location

Where are the citizen scientists completing the tasks¹?

- Online (e.g. through a web platform)
- On site (e.g. in the garden, at the coast, in the mountains, etc.)
- Both online and offline

In case of on-site locations, do participants have all-time and safe access?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

What is the spatial scale for collecting data?

- Small spatial scale (e.g. one specific neighborhood or city)
- Large spatial scale (e.g. multiple cities, or regions)
- Not yet defined

Additional notes:

¹ With tasks, we refer to activity related to the data collection in which the citizen scientists are involved

2. Frequency & timing

How often are citizen scientists expected to participate?

- One time
- On a regular basis

If on a regular basis, what is the desired frequency of data collection?

- Multiple times a day
- Every day
- Several days a week
- Every week
- Several times a month
- Every month
- Other:

How long can citizen scientists participate in the data collection?

- Pre-determined period (e.g. one year)
- There is no pre-determined period
- I do not know

Is there a potential seasonal influence for collecting data?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Does the data collection need to be repeated on a seasonal basis?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Additional notes:

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3. Citizen science tools

Which tool is the citizen scientist using to collect data?

For a list of potential citizen science tools, you can check template X.

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Which tool is the citizen scientist using to analyse data?

For a list of potential citizen science tools, you can check template X.

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Are the citizen science tools freely available?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

How user-friendly are the citizen science tools?

- The tools are very user-friendly
- The tools are somewhat user-friendly
- The tools are rather difficult to use

Additional notes:

4. Efforts, skills, and knowledge

How much time does it take for a citizen scientist to complete a task (data collection and/or data analysis)?

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How demanding is the task for the citizen scientist?

- High effort
- Medium effort
- Low effort

Does the frequency encourage participation?

- It might be that citizen scientists are prompted too frequently and that it might be overwhelming
- There is a structured balance for reporting or analysing data
- It might be that citizen scientists are prompted too infrequently and that they might forget it

Does the task match the skills and knowledge of the citizen scientist?

- The tasks are matched with prior skills and knowledge
- The tasks are new to the citizen scientists and training might be required

Is there a possibility for citizen scientists to progress in regard to the level of difficulty of the tasks?

- Yes, citizen scientists can advance in levels of difficulty
- No, there is only one level of difficulty

Additional notes:

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5. Data quality

To ensure the data quality in your research (project), there are several mechanisms that you can set up during or after the collection of data.

Which mechanisms do you consider implementing for the data collection activities? Consider at least one option:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-testing the data protocol during a trial to identify common errors or deviations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data validation mechanisms (request response options, fixed number of entries, fixed drop-down menus) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control measurements (each observation is collected twice or more)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training of participating citizens (how to guides, videos, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data verification mechanisms (validation by expert users, validation of a random sample, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The law of large numbers (collect a large amount of data on which you can make statistical corrections)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematically dividing a location into segments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic frequency of data collection (seasonal, weekly, yearly, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other: